

Attitude of Physicians Toward Patient Experience in Primary Health Care Settings, Riyadh, Saudi Arabia

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Abstract

Background: Patient experience is defined as reflecting the events in the care process. Therefore, it provides relevant information about the performance of the healthcare system and workers in meeting the patient's needs. It is considered to be an essential outcome of healthcare quality.

Objective: This study aims to assess the Attitude of primary health care (PHC) physicians toward patient experience in Prince Sultan Military Medical City (PSMMC).

Materials and Methods: This study was conducted among working primary healthcare physicians in PSMMC, Saudi Arabia, in March 2022. A three-part self-administered questionnaire was used; the first part was on the participants' sociodemographic, academic, and work profiles. The second part consists of 13 questions assessing the Attitude assessed on a Likert scale of 5 points, and the last part concerns physicians' practice on patient experience. The data that was gathered from the survey was analyzed with the help of SPSS.

Results: The total number of participants was 173 physicians representing the PHC physicians in PSMMC, with a response rate of 94%. The average Attitude of PHC physicians toward the Patient experience is (4.33), considered a high level. The best score was given for the definition of patient experience (4.45 points), followed by the role of communication between Physician and patient on patient experience (4.43 points). The lowest score is given to the recommendation to CBAHI to enhance physician-patient communication as an accreditation standard. The SHO category shows the lowest attitude score (3.7909) in comparison with other categories of positions with significant statistical differences. The average Practice of physicians toward patient Experience is (4.15), considered a high level with no statistically significant differences between different categories.

Conclusion: This study showed that PHC physicians in PSMMC had an overall positive attitude and Practice toward the patient experience, with the SHO physicians obtaining a lower level than the rest of the categories.

Introduction

The healthcare industry is becoming competitive as patients steer their healthcare choices toward providers delivering positive experiences [1]. This transformation brings the issue of experience management in healthcare organizations under the spotlight, and patient experience (P.X.) turns into a critical driver of performance [2]. Patient experience is defined as a reflection of the events in the care process. Therefore, it provides relevant information about the performance of the healthcare system and workers to

meet the patient's needs [3,4]. Patient-experience surveys have been adapted from consumer surveys and applied to the healthcare context internationally, mainly in primary care settings. [5].

Patient experience is a measure of patient-centeredness, one of six healthcare quality aims proposed by the Institute of Medicine (IOM) [6]. A fundamental way to assess whether care is patient-centered is by surveying people interacting with the healthcare system. Patient experience is increasingly recognized as a quality pillar in healthcare alongside

More Information

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Attitude,
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clinical effectiveness and patient safety [7]. The World Health Organisation (WHO) has similarly advocated using the patient's perspective. Further, it supports patient feedback as an essential source of information when developing action plans for Quality Improvement (Q.I.) in health care organisations [8].

Patient experience is an essential outcome of healthcare quality [9], Moreover, patient-reported experiences are vital to improving the quality of care [3,4]. Increasing attention is being paid to the patient experience as an indicator of healthcare quality, as a measure that can identify shortcomings, improve healthcare quality, and promote patients' choice and voice [10].

Patient Satisfaction Vs. Patient Experience

A subtle yet significant change in the years since the IOM reports was replacing "patient satisfaction" with "patient experience." The change reflects the realization that the challenges for healthcare go beyond meeting or exceeding consumers' expectations (i.e., satisfying them); the real goal is to meet their needs with reliability, efficiency, and safety. Whereas "patient satisfaction" is based on whether the care conforms to patients' expectations, "patient experience" incorporates everything that directly or indirectly affects patients across the continuum of care, including the relief of their suffering, physical discomfort, and anxiety. Interestingly, some of the first validated measures of patient satisfaction within private industry, such as the Press Ganey instrument, evaluated a full complement of the patient experience (e.g., communication, respect, shared decision-making, privacy, preparation for discharge). However, because early studies found that overall patient evaluation measures were associated with malpractice risk, much of the work focused on improving overall perceptions to avoid risk rather than enhancing quality for the various elements of patient care [11].

According to WHO (2021), the concept of PHC has been redefined since 1978, leading to confusion about the term and its Practice. A clear definition has been developed to facilitate coordinated PHC efforts globally, nationally, and locally and guide implementation.

Primary Health Care (PHC) is an approach to healthcare that involves all aspects of society. It aims to promote the highest possible well-being and ensure equitable health service distribution by addressing people's healthcare needs, from prevention to palliative care. PHC is designed to be accessible to people within their daily environment. This vision for primary healthcare in the 21st century is a step towards Universal Health Coverage (UHC) and the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) proposed by WHO and UNICEF.

Primary Health Care (PHC) comprises three interrelated and synergistic components. The first component is

comprehensive, integrated health services, including primary care and public health goods and functions. The second component involves multi-sectoral policies and actions to address the broader determinants of health. The third component involves involving and empowering individuals, families, and communities to ensure they participate socially and improve their self-care in health.

These three components work together to comprehensively and effectively meet the healthcare needs of individuals, families, and communities. PHC is committed: "Everyone has the right to enjoy the highest attainable standard of health. Primary Health Care (PHC) emphasizes that governments at all levels should prioritize actions beyond the health sector. They should adopt a whole-of-government approach to health that includes health-in-all-policies, focuses on equity, and provides interventions encompassing the entire life course.

Primary Health Care (PHC) considers the broader determinants of health and focuses on the holistic and interconnected aspects of physical, mental, and social health and well-being. Primary healthcare (PHC) offers a complete range of health services that cater to people's needs throughout their lifespan rather than just treating specific illnesses. The services provided by PHC include health promotion, disease prevention, treatment, rehabilitation, and palliative care. This care is provided as close to their daily environment as possible. Primary Health Care (PHC) considers the broader determinants of health and focuses on the holistic and interconnected aspects of physical, mental, and social health and well-being. It provides comprehensive care for health needs across the lifespan, not just for specific illnesses.

Role of Physicians in Patient Experience

Physician-patient communication, a core measure of patient-centered care, is strongly associated with better clinical health outcomes. This factor can be measured differently, and some aspects contribute to a better patient experience. For example, a physician's ability to listen and explain diagnoses and treatment options is an essential indicator of the quality of physician-patient communication [12,13]. According to a 2002 study by Thom, patients with less trust in their physicians are likelier to request or demand necessary services. Understanding this correlation could help medical professionals respond to patient requests in a way that preserves or improves their trust, ultimately leading to better health outcomes.

According to [14], our research indicates that when measuring patients' experience at the practice level, significant variations might exist between individual doctors within a practice. Our findings suggest that higher-performing practices usually consist of higher-performing doctors. However, lower-performing

practices may have doctors with communication scores ranging from poor to very good. When assessing non-doctor-specific practice-related attributes, such as cleanliness of facilities, patient ratings are consistent across the practice.

[15] It is necessary to obtain more clarity regarding the purpose of providing patient assessment feedback to individual doctors. Specifically, it is essential to determine who should be responsible for giving feedback and how to deliver it most effectively. We must understand whether feedback improves doctor performance and whether these evaluations correlate with other physician attributes.

There needs to be more evidence that feedback on its own or feedback with brief training improves doctors' consultation skills [16].

[17] conducted a study that revealed doctors often criticize patients' motivations and competence while emphasizing patient-centered care. This undermines the potential for survey-based quality improvement and highlights the importance of patient feedback. The study found that doctors working in different healthcare settings show similarly complex and contradictory attitudes toward the plausibility of patient feedback. This can limit the potential impact of patient experience surveys on care delivery. In response, the study's authors emphasize the need for a 'sense-giving' dialogue among policymakers, managers, and clinicians to address doctors' concerns about the plausibility of surveys. Effective communication between physicians and patients is also crucial to patient satisfaction, which can significantly affect overall satisfaction [18].

As per a study conducted by [19], doctors play a vital role in ensuring a positive care experience for patients. In Ontario's primary healthcare setting, family health teams and community health centers must use surveys to assess patient experience. According to a report by [4], clinicians and patients found primary care streaming acceptable when they received prompt and suitable care for their complaints. Additionally, effective communication by clinicians regarding investigations and their role in decision-making and treatment plans was also reported to contribute to a positive care experience.

[20] identifies a strong correlation between physician-patient communication and patient satisfaction.

Patient Experience in PHC

It is important to consider patients' opinions when evaluating primary healthcare services. To improve patient satisfaction, people must understand the nature and purpose of primary care reforms. Furthermore, personal choice of primary care doctor and establishing good patient-doctor relationships are crucial factors in ensuring quality healthcare [21].

Several authors have conducted studies to evaluate patients' satisfaction with medical healthcare services, especially in primary care. These studies were carried out in the context of the European project (European et al. on Patient Evaluation of General Practice) using an internationally developed tool to assess general practice care from the patient's perspective. The research consistently demonstrated that patients were delighted with the care they received. Doctors acknowledge the importance of patient feedback in improving patient experience, as highlighted by previous studies such as [15,22,23].

The tools and concept of measuring patient experience sit comfortably in the 'personalized' healthcare domain, particularly in family medicine, where the patient-centered method was developed and promoted to become an accepted paradigm across all healthcare disciplines [24].

The participating G.P.s regarded patient feedback as highly important. They monitored it constantly during their daily interactions. Still, they felt that patient-experience surveys, as currently implemented, needed a more explicit purpose and needed to be easier to interpret and respond to in terms of training or changing their consultation behaviors [24].

[25] conducted a study to highlight the benefits of using multilevel analysis in understanding patient satisfaction scores. The study found that strategies aimed at improving the quality of healthcare services by targeting healthcare providers or services based solely on general satisfaction scores may need to be revised. Instead, more emphasis should be placed on analyzing the interaction process between the patient and their general practitioner (G.P.) to improve patient satisfaction. A study conducted by [4] found that patients referred to and seen by primary care clinicians were highly satisfied with their experience. The study was based on qualitative interviews with patients and clinicians and led to developing a program theory. Effective communication is essential for patient satisfaction. Providers should actively seek patient feedback.

Patient Experience Internationally

In England, patient experience is measured by surveys, including the General Practice Patient Survey (GPPS) in primary care and the Inpatient Survey in secondary care [26]. [27] conducted a study highlighting that patients place value on factors such as ease of scheduling appointments, availability of information, communication with clinicians, responsiveness of clinic staff, and coordination between care providers. To delve further into a patient's overall experience, additional questions can be added to the primary survey to assess how the provider engages the patient as a whole person and how they involve them in

decision-making, disease management, and health promotion.

Regarding managerial support, it is shown that perceived supervisor support positively influences patient experience through perceived organizational support and advocacy for employees [28].

Patient Experience and PHC in KSA

Locally, the importance of practitioner-patient interaction and its influence on the care experience has been highlighted in the study [29]. Also, [30] found that a patient's trust in a PHC is strongly associated with effective and clear communication between a patient and Physician.

The biggest challenge in primary healthcare in Saudi Arabia is the communication gap between patients and physicians, as doctors come from diverse backgrounds and speak different languages. According to [31], cultural and linguistic differences are the two major obstacles to effective communication between patients and physicians.

A systematic review was done by [32] to explore patient satisfaction (P.S.) among patients who used the Ministry of Health (MoH) primary care centers in Saudi Arabia, with a focus on their communication with physicians. There needed to be more consistency between the patient's responses to the surveys on the domains of P.S. and their experience. While the patients reported being satisfied with primary care centers, they frequently attended the emergency department directly. This indicated they were unlikely to be fully satisfied with the primary healthcare center [32].

According to a study, physicians answering patient questions was the most significant predictor of the overall rating in this model. The second most important factor was the time spent with the physician, followed by the type of primary healthcare center (PHC) and the physician's abilities to listen carefully, explain things clearly, and show respect. The weakest predictors were the healthcare provider's follow-ups and physicians' knowledge of the patient's medical history.

Recent research emphasizes the need for improved doctor-patient communication to enhance care quality and patients' experience at Primary Health Centers (PHCs). The Ministry of Health must ensure that interpretation services are available for patients at public and private PHCs to achieve this goal. Moreover, the Saudi Central Board for Accreditation of Healthcare Institutions (CBAHI) should focus on physician-patient communication as a vital aspect of its standards for accrediting PHCs [30].

As a part of Saudi Vision 2030, improving the patient experience has been identified as a crucial element for enhancing the quality and efficiency of healthcare services. This initiative is a part of the Health Sector Transformation Program (HSTP), which aims to prepare

the healthcare sector to realize Vision 2030. After conducting a detailed study to identify the lessons learned from the COVID-19 pandemic, the HSTP has proposed this initiative as one of its priority projects [33].

In Saudi Arabia, Physicians are the first point of contact for patients at primary healthcare centers (PHCs). In Saudi Arabia, health services can be accessed through 2 routes. Patients can first use the health services provided by PHCs and subsequently be referred to secondary care. Alternatively, patients can bypass the PHCs to receive care at the emergency department (E.D.), followed by visits to outpatient clinics for further secondary care.

According to a study by [30], enhancing physician-patient communication is crucial for improving the overall patient experience and the quality of care at Primary Health Centers (PHCs). To achieve this, the Ministry of Health should ensure that interpretation services are available to patients at public and private PHCs. Additionally, the Saudi Central Board for Accreditation of Healthcare Institutions should make physician-patient communication a part of their standards for accrediting PHCs. Improving communication can improve quality, safety, and efficiency in healthcare services.

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Patient Experience in PHC of PSMMC

A patient experience survey was conducted in the fourth quarter of 2021 in the primary health care centers (PHC) affiliated with the Medical Services Department (MSD) in the Ministry of Defense in Riyadh by the Press Jenny website in regional partnership with Health Links Company. The overall performance score was 65.67, compared to an average score of 73.91 in the rest of the MSD primary healthcare centers. This means that it is below the average by -8.24. Regarding the Physician's domain assessment, the patient's experience was 68.36 compared to the MSD average score of 72.85, which means it is below the MSD score by -4 [35].

And because of the Press Ganey/Health. Links survey in evaluating the patient's experience give more weighted scores to the domains related to the patient's interaction with physicians compared to the rest of the domains, as the number of questions related to dealing with the doctor is 10 out of 38 questions for the rest of the departments and services within the primary health

care centers, which means That the side of physicians has the most significant impact on the reflection of the patient's experience. [36].

The Research importance

The patient experience program is crucial for enhancing healthcare quality and improving health organizations' performance. It is one of the main pillars of the national transformation program in the health sector, which is part of the Saudi Arabia 2030 vision. In light of this, a research study has been initiated to evaluate physicians' attitudes toward the patient experience program.

Rationale of study

In light of the preceding, the researcher focused on studying Physicians' attitudes towards the patient experience in the primary health care centers of the Prince Sultan Military Medical City (PSMMC), affiliated with the Medical Services Department (MSD) in the Ministry of Defense.

Research Problem

According to the patient experience program report, doctors at primary healthcare centers in Prince Sultan Military Medical City (PSMMC) received a low score for their performance during the fourth quarter of 2022. This score was lower than that of primary healthcare centers affiliated with the Medical Services Department (MSD). This affected the overall evaluation of the patient experience in primary healthcare centers.

Research Objectives

To assess the Attitude of primary health care (PHC) physicians in Prince Sultan Military Medical City (PSMMC) toward Patient Experience during 2022.

Research Questions

1. What is the Attitude of primary health care (PHC) physicians in Prince Sultan Military Medical City (PSMMC) toward Patient Experience?
2. What is the Practice of PHC physicians in PSMMC toward patient Experience?

Research Hypothesis

A literature review of previous research found that physicians are the most influential element in the patient's experience. Therefore, a physician's negative Attitude will be reflected negatively in the patient's experience results, and vice versa.

Scientific Contribution

Due to the scarcity of research published locally and internationally that measures physicians' attitudes toward the patient experience, we decided to conduct this study as the first study of its kind. We wanted to contribute scientifically to studying primary healthcare physicians' attitudes toward patient experience.

Research Limitations

Time limitation: This study has a time limitation.

Financial limitation: There is no financial support for purchasing data analysis software such as SPSS.

Literature Review

In the USA, the Attitudes began to change in 2000, with the publication of To Err Is Human, a landmark Institute of Medicine (IOM) report on patient safety [37] and its 2001 successor, Crossing the Quality Chasm. In combination, these two reports revealed enormous problems in healthcare quality in the United States. What we had previously assumed to be consistently high-quality care was now revealed to be frequently unreliable and inadequate in meeting patient needs. Although much of the initial attention focused on patient safety, the reports—particularly the second—highlighted other issues. Recommendations included the following:

- Healthcare should always be responsive to patients' needs (i.e., 24 hours daily).
- The care system should be designed to meet the most common needs and be flexible enough to accommodate individuals' needs and values.
- Patients should be the source of control, with all the necessary information and the opportunity to exercise as much control as they want over healthcare decisions that affect them.

Effective communication and information-sharing between healthcare providers and patients is crucial for better health outcomes.

- The health system should anticipate patients' needs, not just respond to events.
- Clinicians and organizations should cooperate, communicate, and coordinate their efforts.

Patient-experience surveys have been adapted from consumer surveys and applied to the healthcare context internationally, mainly in primary care settings. [5].

The World Health Organisation (WHO) has similarly advocated using the patient's perspective. Further, it supports patient feedback as an essential source of information when developing action plans for Quality Improvement (Q.I.) in health care organisations [8].

Physicians are the first point of contact for patients at primary healthcare centers (PHCs). In Saudi Arabia, health services can be accessed through 2 routes. Patients can first use the health services provided by PHCs and subsequently be referred to secondary care. Alternatively, patients can bypass the PHCs to receive care at the emergency department (E.D.), followed by visits to outpatient clinics for further secondary care.

A study conducted by Browne et al. in 2010 revealed that various factors determine patient value. These factors include ease of scheduling appointments, access to information, communication with healthcare providers, promptness of clinic staff, and coordination between different healthcare providers involved in the patient's care. It is recommended to include additional question sets in the survey to evaluate how well the healthcare provider engages with the patient as a

whole person. This includes decision-making, disease management, and health promotion.

In England, patient experience is measured by surveys, including the General Practice Patient Survey (GPPS) in primary care and the Inpatient Survey in secondary care [26].

It is important to consider patients' opinions when evaluating Primary Health Care (PHC). To increase patient satisfaction, people must understand the purpose and objective of the primary care reforms. Personal choice of primary care physician and positive patient-doctor relationships are also crucial factors that contribute to overall satisfaction [21].

Several authors have evaluated patients' satisfaction with healthcare services in primary care, specifically as part of the European project, the European Patient Evaluation of General Practice. They used an internationally developed tool to evaluate general practice care from the patient's point of view. These studies consistently found that patients reported a high level of satisfaction. Research shows that doctors value patient experience, and improvements can be made based on patient feedback. This has been highlighted in studies conducted by [15,22,23] among others.

Doctors criticize patients' abilities and motivations while promoting patient-centered care, which undermines the potential for using patient feedback to improve the quality of healthcare services. Two different healthcare settings have similar, complex, and contradictory attitudes toward the usefulness of patient feedback, which can limit the impact of patient experience surveys on care delivery. To address this issue, policymakers, managers, and clinicians must engage in a dialogue addressing doctors' concerns about using surveys to improve healthcare services.

The tools and concept of measuring patient experience sit comfortably in the 'personalized' healthcare domain, particularly in family medicine, where the patient-centered method was developed and promoted to become an accepted paradigm across all healthcare disciplines [24].

The participating G.P.s regarded patient feedback as highly important. They monitored it constantly during their daily interactions. Still, they felt that patient-experience surveys, as currently implemented, needed a more explicit purpose and needed to be easier to interpret and respond to in terms of training or changing their consultation behaviors [24].

The research conducted by [15] highlights the need for more clarity in providing patient assessment feedback to individual doctors. It specifies who should give the feedback and how it should be done to achieve the best results. It is essential to determine whether feedback improves doctor performance and how these evaluations correlate with other physician attributes.

According to [14] study, measuring patients' experience at the practice level can mask significant variation between doctors. The study suggests that higher-performing practices usually comprise higher-performing doctors. However, lower-performing practices may contain doctors with communication scores ranging from poor to very good. When patients' ratings focus on non-doctor-specific practice-related attributes, such as cleanliness, these are measured well at the practice level.

The study conducted by [25] highlights the importance of using multilevel analysis to study patient satisfaction scores. The findings suggest that there needs to be more than just general satisfaction scores to improve the quality of care from the patient's perspective. In other words, strategies to enhance healthcare providers or services should not be solely based on general satisfaction scores. The study emphasizes the need to focus on the interaction process between patients and healthcare providers, especially G.P.s, to enhance the quality of care.

There needs to be more evidence that feedback on its own or feedback with brief training improves doctors' consultation skills [16].

To enhance the quality of care and the overall patient experience in Primary Health Centers (PHCs), paying particular attention to the communication between physicians and patients is crucial. Seitan & Gillespie (2019) recommend that the Ministry of Health offer interpretation services for patients at public and private PHCs to improve quality, safety, and efficiency. Additionally, the Saudi Central Board for Accreditation of Healthcare Institutions should incorporate Physician-patient communication improvement as part of their accreditation standards for PHCs.

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Methodology

This study deals with patient experience due to its importance in improving health services. It aims to assess the attitudes of primary healthcare physicians in Prince Sultan Military Medical City (PSMMC) towards the patient experience program during 2022.

Research Design

The type of Research

The research will be conducted using a primary observational descriptive cross-sectional study. This type of study is Cheap and quick, and data is frequently available through records or statistics. In addition, it is

ideal for generating a new hypothesis and providing clues for further research.

Research Approach

The study approach is deductive reasoning. It uses quantitative data from a survey questionnaire to assess the association between physicians' attitudes and low-performance patient experience scores.

Study Population

The study population was determined to be the physicians working in the primary health care centers in PSMMC affiliated with the Ministry of Defense Health Services (MSD) in Riyadh during 2023.

Rotating residents and fellow physicians visiting from outside PSMMC were excluded because they were not administratively affiliated with the organization and because of their temporary presence in the PSMMC's primary health centers.

Study Period

The study data has been collected within December 2023.

Sampling Technique

Due to the uneven distribution of physicians among the health centers, stratified systematic sampling was used to select the study sample. Through it, the sampling frame (study population) was made for each center (stratum) using a list of physicians' tables in all PSMMC healthcare centers. Then, Physicians were selected proportionally to the size of physicians in each center by using systematic sampling to ensure that all communities of physicians were represented with the same probability of being selected.

Sample Size

The total number of primary health care physicians in PSMMC is around 350, distributed unequally in 20 centers. Statistical packages (Epi Info.) were used to calculate sample size. One hundred seventy-five or more surveys are needed to have a confidence level of 95% (level of statistical significance at 0.05).

The sampling frame is presented as a list of physicians in the serial number for each center. Then, a sampling ratio of 1 in K (K = sampling interval = 2).

The first respondent's selection starting point was random, followed by every second unit from the Physician's list for each center.

Bias

This study is susceptible to selection bias due to sampling and low response, information bias due to Recall, and confounding bias due to the inability to collect information on all potential confounders.

Research Method/Technique/Tool

A self-administered questionnaire will be used as a data collection tool, in which respondents write down their answers to written questions electronically.

The questionnaire is structured into the following sections:

1- Introduction & Instructions: Explain clearly the purpose of the study, confidentiality, use of data, and potential benefit of data.

2- Sociodemographic information: personal data (e.g., age, gender, level of education, experience, and Position of Physician...)

3- The primary study Questions assess the Attitude of physicians toward Patient Experience by using the Likert scale.

4- Closing statement: Thank the respondent.

- Closed-ended questions were used in the questionnaire to analyze responses and stimulate Recall quickly.

- Likert-style questions will be used to assess the attitudes of physicians.

- The questionnaire will be electronically distributed to the selected physicians through email containing a link to an online survey.

- The questionnaire will be built from several literature reviews. Its validity will be assessed in two stages: face validity by untrained judges and content validity by three specialized experts. After that, test-retest reliability will be evaluated using a correlation coefficient (r-value).

- A Dummy table of desired data will be drawn based on the questionnaire to ensure that all information required can be captured.

Data Analysis

- Data was analyzed using IBM® SPSS® Statistics version 22 (IBM® et al., USA).

- Appropriate statistical tests (Chi-square, ANOVA) will be used accordingly, and P-values were considered statistically significant if <0.05 .

- Graphical Presentation (bar chart & pie chart) and Tables will be used for variable description.

Ethical Approval

IRB in Prince Sultan Military Medical City has approved this research project with IRB Approval No# E-2214.

Informed consent will be ensured before the questionnaire is completed. The participants were also granted confidentiality, anonymity, and voluntary participation.

Limitation

This cross-sectional study is Susceptible to selection bias because of sampling and low response. It is also susceptible to information bias because of Recall and confounding bias due to the inability to collect information on all potential confounders.

Results

This research project aimed to study the Physician's Attitude toward the patient experience program in the primary health care centers of the Prince Sultan Military Medical City (PSMMC) affiliated with the Medical Services Department (MSD) in the Ministry of Defense. They assessed the Attitudes and Practices of PHC physicians toward patient experience and its

association with different demographic variables from randomly selected physicians via an electronic survey. Then, the results of the study were to offer valuable contributions to raising awareness of the importance of the patient experience to physicians, which Reflects on the performance of health centers in general.

The research study was conducted over 14 days, starting from 20 March 2022, and the consent form was given to each participant in the electronic questionnaire. One hundred seventy-three participants completed the electronic survey successfully, with a response rate of 94%. The questionnaire's stability was tested using Cronbach's Alpha to ensure the reliability between several items and response measurements in questionnaire validity. In Table (1), the everyday reliability of "Attitude" is 0.951, "Practice" is 0.776, and the everyday reliability of all phrases of study is 0.896; this indicates questionnaire reliability is high, especially in field applications for studying and also it is results dependable for Nunnally, it is accepted 0.70 a minimum rate.

Table 1: Questionnaire Stability

Cronbach's Alpha	
Attitude	0.951
Practice	0.776
All phrases	0.896

The study used questionnaires to gather information on various demographic factors such as age, gender, post-MBBS qualification, position, nationality, and years of experience. Additionally, the physicians' attitudes toward patient experience were assessed by examining the existing literature on patient experience, patient-centeredness, and their roles in improving the quality and performance of healthcare services. Finally, the study looked at the practice variables of physicians that affect patient experience in clinical situations, such as how courteous they are to patients, how concerned they are about their worries, and whether they provide enough time for consultation.

All data were then collected through Microsoft Excel and analyzed using IBM® SPSS® Statistics version 22 (IBM® et al., USA) for performing descriptive and inferential statistics. T-tests and ANOVA were run to predict statistically significant differences in each demographic factor (gender, qualification, age, nationality variables), Attitude, and practice levels of PHC physicians toward patient experience. P-values were considered statistically significant if <0.05.

Demographic Factors

The findings show that about half of the total sample, 49.7% of their aged interval (31-40), followed by (41-50), 22.5%, and 19.7% (20-30), while 8.1% (50 and more), as shown in Table (2).

Table 2: Shows the Distribution of the Sample (N=173) According to Their Age

Variable	Statement	Frequency	Percent
Age	20-30	14	19.7%
	31-40	86	49.7%
	41-50	39	22.5%
	51 and more	14	8.1%
	Total	173	100%

Table 3: Shows the Distribution of the Sample (N=173) According to Their Gender

Variable	Statement	Frequency	Percent
Gender	Male	91	52.6%
	Female	82	47.4%
	Total	173	100%

Table (3) shows that 52.6% of the total sample was (male), while 47.4% was female.

From Table (4), the findings show that the highest percentage of the sample (33.5%) have experience between (11-15), followed by (24.9%) having (6-10) years of experience. 17.3% of the participants have (0-5) years of experience, while only (16.3%) of the participants have (16-20) years of experience, and finally (7.5%) have experience More than 20 years.

Table 4: Shows the Distribution of the Sample (N=173) According to Their Experience in PHC

Variable	Statement	Frequency	Percent
Experience in PHC	0-5	30	17.4%
	6-10	43	24.9%
	11-15	58	33.5%
	16-20	28	16.3%
	21 and more	13	7.6%
	Total	173	100%

Table 5: Shows the Distribution of the Sample (N=173) According to Their Marital Status

Variable	Statement	Frequency	Percent
marital status	Single	36	20.9%
	Married	131	76.2%
	Divorce	5	2.9%
	Total	173	100%

Table (5) shows that most of the total sample (76.2%) were married, followed by singles (20.9%), while only 2.9% were divorced.

Table (6) shows that the highest percentage of the sample (34.1%) were qualified by their Board of equivalent post-MBBS, followed by 21.4% of the sample with no post-MBBS qualification (Nil), followed by 19.1% with a master's, 17.9% with Fellowship equivalent, and finally 7.1% with a diploma.

Table 6: Shows the Distribution of the Sample (N=173) According to Their Post MBBS Qualification

Variable	Statement	Frequency	Percent
Post MBBS Qualification	Nil	37	21.4%
	Diploma	13	7.5%
	Master	33	19.1%
	Board of equivalent	59	34.1%
	Fellowship equivalent	31	17.9%
	Total	173	100%

Table 7: Shows the Distribution of the Sample (N=173) According to Their Nationality

Variable	Statement	Frequency	Percent
Nationality	Saudi	84	48.6%
	Non-Saudi (Arabic speaking)	63	36.4%
	Non-Saudi (Non-Arabic speaking)	26	15.0%
	Total	173	100%

Table (7) shows that nearly half of the total sample (48.6%) were Saudi, followed by 36.4% who were non-Saudi (Arabic speaking) and 15% who were non-Saudi (non-Arabic speaking).

Table (8) The findings show that the highest percentage of the total sample was (Registrar) at 40.5%, followed by (Residents) at 19.7%, followed by(Consultant) at

17.4%, followed by (Senior Registrar) at 14%. In comparison, 8% of the total sample was.

Table 8: Shows the Distribution of the Sample (N=173) According to Their Position

Variable	Statement	Frequency	Percent
Position	Senior House Officer (SHO)	14	8.1%
	Resident	34	19.8%
	Registrar	70	40.7%
	Senior Registrar	24	14.0%
	Consultant	30	17.4%
	Total	173	100%

The Attitude of PHC Physicians Toward Patient Experience

Table (9) shows (Descriptive statistics about the Attitude of Physicians toward Patient Experience, which refer to the extent of PHC physician's Agreement and beliefs toward patient experience concepts developed from different literature reviews. The findings showed the highest average was awarded to phrase number 1 (Patient experience is defined as a reflection of the events that occur in the health care process), with (M=4.45, STD 0.686), followed by phrase 8 Communication between the Physician and patient is a significant component of Patient Satisfaction that can affect overall satisfaction) with (M=4.43, STD 0.709), followed by phrase10 (supervisor support has

Table 9: Descriptive Statistic for "Attitude of Physicians toward Patient Experience"

Questions		Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Mean	Std. deviation	Rank
Patient experience is defined as a reflection of the events that occur in the health care process	N	96	60	16	1	0	4.45	0.686	1
	%	55.5	34.7	9.2	0.6	0			
Patient experience is a measure of patient-centeredness	N	82	62	27	2	0	4.29	0.770	12
	%	47.4	35.8	15.6	1.2	0			
Patient Experience provides relevant information about the performance of the healthcare system and workers to meet the needs of the patient	N	88	64	20	1	0	4.38	0.710	4
	%	50.9	37.0	11.6	0.6	0			
Patient experience is an essential outcome of healthcare quality	N	81	67	24	1	0	4.32	0.729	8
	%	46.8	38.7	13.9	0.6	0			
	N	81	67	22	2	0	4.32	0.739	9

patient-reported experiences are vital to improving the quality of care	%	46.8	38.7	12.7	1.2	0			
Physician-patient communication, a core measure of patient-centered care, is strongly associated with better clinical health outcomes	N	88	60	22	3	0	4.35	0.767	5
	%	50.9	34.7	12.7	1.7	0			
Patients with a lower level of trust in their Physician are more likely to report that requested or needed services are not provided.	N Patients who trust their physicians are more likely to receive requested or needed services.	81	67	23	2	0	4.31	0.744	11
	%	46.8	38.7	13.3	1.2	0			
Communication between the Physician and patient is a significant component of Patient Satisfaction that can affect overall satisfaction	N	96	57	19	1	0	4.43	0.709	2
	%	55.5	32.9	11.0	0.6	0			
Patients' opinions are essential in the evaluation of PHC	N	88	57	26	2	0	4.34	0.772	7
	%	50.9	32.9	15.0	1.2	0			
supervisor support has a positive indirect influence on patient experience through perceived organizational support and advocacy for employees	N	90	61	22	0	0	4.39	0.704	3
	%	62.0	35.3	12.7	0	0			
A patient's trust in a PHC is strongly associated with effective and clear communication between a patient and a Physician.	N	88	55	30	0	0	4.34	0.757	6
	%	50.9	31.8	17.3	0	0			
The highest predictor of the overall rating in patient experience is physicians answering patient questions,	N	82	62	29	0	0	4.31	0.742	10
	%	47.4	36.8	16.8	0	0			
The Saudi Central Board for Accreditation of Healthcare Institutions (CBAHI) should enhance physician-patient communication as part of their standards for accrediting PHCs.	N	63	62	45	2	1	4.06	0,850	13
	%	36.4	35.8	26.0	1.2	0.6			
The Attitude of Physicians toward Patient Experience							4.33	0.59	

A positive indirect influence on patient experience through perceived organizational support and employee advocacy.) with a mean (M=4.39, STD 0.704). The lowest average was awarded to the phrase 13 (The Saudi Central Board for Accreditation of Healthcare Institutions (CBAHI) should enhance physician-patient

communication as part of their standards for accrediting PHCs.), with (M=4.06, STD 0.850). The average weight of the Attitude of Physicians toward Patient Experience) is 4.33, with Std. A deviation of 0.59 indicates that the trend of the Attitude of Physicians toward Patient Experience) is (Strongly agrees) as a general trend according to the 5-

point Likert scale shown in Table (10) below since 4.33 lies in the interval [4.20-5.00].So the average of the (Attitude of Physicians toward Patient Experience) is (4.33), which is considered a "High level," which means "PHC physician's Agreement and beliefs toward patient experience concepts is very high, since the intervals of the level shown in table(11).

Table 10: Likert Scale Degrees

Likert scale	Categories
Strongly Disagree	[1.00 - 1.79]
Disagree	[1.80 - 2.59]
Neutral	[2.60 - 3.39]
Agree	[3.40 - 4.19]
Strongly agree Agree	[4.20 - 5.00]

Table 11: Level Degrees

Low level	[1 - 2.59]
Moderate level	[2.60 - 3.39]
High level	[3.40 - 5]

From table(12) :

The t-test result is 0.413, with a p-value =0.680 greater than 0.05. Therefore, we have decided that there is no statistically significant gender difference in the Attitude of primary health care (PHC) physicians toward patient experience.

Table 12: Shows T test for Different According to Gender

		N	Mean	Std. deviation	t value	P values	Significant
gender	Male	91	4.2335	0.4039	0.413	0.680	Not significant
	Female	82	4.2596	0.4272			

Table 13: Shows the ANOVA Test for Different Demographic Variable

		Mean	F value	P values	Significant
Age	20-30	4.1856	0.791	0.501	Not significant
	31-40	4.2307			
	41-50	4.3281			
	51 and more	4.2560			
Experience in PHC	0-5	4.0819	2.020	0.094	Not significant
	6-10	4.2525			
	11-15	4.2832			
	16-20	4.3700			
	21 and more	4.2000			
marital status	Single	4.1468	1.502	0.226	Not significant
	Married	4.2791			
	Divorce	4.1923			
Post MBBS Qualification	Nil	4.1452	1.335	0.259	Not significant
	Diploma	4.1825			
	Master	4.3661			
	Board of equivalent	4.2495			
	Fellowship equivalent	4.2576			
Nationality	Saudi	4.2396	0.969	0.374	Not significant
	Non-Saudi (Arabic speaking)	4.2911			
	Non-Saudi (Non-Arabic speaking)	4.1567			

Table (14): Shows ANOVA Test for Different According to Demographic Variable

		Mean	F value	P values	Significant
Position	Senior House Officer (SHO)	3.7909	6.389	0.000 **	significant
	Resident	4.3569			
	Registrar	4.3191			
	Senior Registrar	4.3800			
	Consultant	4.2007			

** Significant at 0.01

Table (14) finds that the p-value = (0.000) is smaller than 0.05. Therefore, there are statistically significant differences between the Attitudes of Primary Health Care (PHC) Physicians toward Patient Experience due to position. This means primary health care (PHC)

physicians' attitudes toward patient experience are influenced by physician position. The researcher used multiple comparative (Scheffe) tests to determine the reason for the differences.

Table 15: Shows the Scheffe Test

Attitude of Primary Health Care (PHC) Physicians toward Patient Experience	Difference in mean	P-value	Significant
Resident -----Senior house officer	0.4680	0.007	Significant
Registrar-----Senior house officer	0.5281	0.000	Significant
S- registrar----- Senior house officer	0.5890	0.001	Significant
Consultant ----Senior house officer	0.4097	0.031	Significant

From Table (15), findings show the SHO physicians, despite their high level of Attitude toward the patient experience according to the Likert scale (3.79), are the lowest compared to their colleagues of different positions with statically significant differences while the senior registrars were the highest in the level of Attitude (4.38), followed by resident (4.36), then registrars (4.32), and finally consultants (4.2) with no statistically significant differences.

The Practice of PHC physicians toward the patient experience

Table (16): This shows Descriptive statistics for the Practice of physicians toward patient Experience, in which findings show that the highest average was awarded to phrase number 1 (I show friendliness/courtesy to the patient), with (M=4.73, STD 0.445) and followed by phrase 2 (I explain to the patient about their problem or condition) with (M=4.49, STD 0.534), followed by phrase3 (I show

concern for patient questions or worries) with (M=4.48, STD 0.555).

The lowest average was awarded to phrase 5 (I Give detailed information to the patient about their medications), with (M=3.48, STD 1.092), followed by phrase 10 (I Seek the patient's recommendation for other patients to visit me), with (M=3.76, STD 1.120). The average weight of the practice of physicians toward patient Experience) is 4.15, with a Std Deviation of 0.46, which indicates that the trend of (Practice of physicians toward patient Experience) is (Often) a general trend according to the 5-point Likert scale shown in Table (17) below since 4.15 lies in the interval [3.40-4.19].

So the average of the "Practice of physicians toward patient Experience, or The behavior of PHC physicians toward the patient experience based on different patient experience surveys), is (4.15), which is considered a High level since the intervals of the level shown in the Table (18).

Table 16: Descriptive Statistic for " Practice of Physicians toward Patient Experience "

Questions		Always	Often	Sometimes	Rarely	Never	Mean	Std. deviation	Rank
I show friendliness/courtesy to the patient	N	126	47	0	0	0	4.73	0.445	1
	%	72.8	27.2	0	0	0			

I explain to the patient about their problem or condition	N	86	85	2	0	0	4.49	0.524	2
	%	49.7	49.1	1.2	0	0			
I show concern for patient questions or worries	N	85	83	5	0	0	4.48	0.555	3
	%	49.1	48	29	0	0			
I include the patient in the decision about their treatment	N	66	84	23	0	0	4.25	0.675	7
	%	38.2	48.6	13.3	0	0			
I Give detailed information to the patient about their medications	N	37	53	39	44	0	3.48	1.092	10
	%	21.4	30.6	22.5	25.4	0			
I Instruct patients about follow-up care (if any)	N	93	70	10	0	0	4.48	0.606	4
	%	53.8	40.5	5.3	0	0			
I Talk to the patient by using words they can understand	N	71	75	23	4	0	4.23	0.765	8
	%	41	43.4	13.3	23	0			
I Give the patient enough amount of time for consultation	N	36	42	59	36	0	3.45	1.042	5
	%	20.8	24.3	34.1	20.8	0			
I Strive to gain patient trust	N	80	66	24	2	1	4.28	0.789	6
	%	46.2	38.2	13.9	1.2	0.6			
I Seek the patient's recommendation for other patients to visit me	N	49	61	45	3	13	3.76	1.120	9
	%	28.3	35.3	26.0	1.7	7.5			
The practice of physicians toward Patient Experience							4.15	0.460	

Table 17: Likert Scale Degrees

Likert scale	Categories
Never	[1.00 - 1.79]
Rarely	[1.80 - 2.59]
Sometimes	[2.60 - 3.39]
Often	[3.40 - 4.19]
Always	[4.20 - 5.00]

Table 18: Level Degrees

Low level	[1 - 2.59]
Moderate level	[2.60 - 3.39]
High level	[3.40 - 5]

Table 19: Shows T-tests for Different According to Gender

		N	Mean	Std. deviation	t value	P values	Significant
gender	Male	91	4.1282	0.4334	0.1008	0.315	Not significant
	Female	82	4.1993	0.4995			

From Table (20), we found that all p-values are better than 0.05, so there are no statistically significant differences between "Practice of physicians toward

From Table (19), we found that:

The t-test result is 0.1008, with a p-value = 0.315 greater than 0.05, so there are no statistically significant differences between physicians' practices regarding patient Experience due to the gender variable.

Are there statistically significant differences between "Practice of physicians toward patient Experience" due to age, experience in PHC, marital status, post-MBBS qualification, nationality, and position? To show that, the researcher used an ANOVA test.

patient Experience " due to age, experience in PHC, marital status, post-MBBS qualification, nationality, and position.

Table (20): Shows ANOVA Test for Different According to Demographic Variable

		Mean	F value	P values	Significant
Age	20-30	4.1676	0.344	0.794	Not significant
	31-40	4.1314			
	41-50	4.3834			
	51 and more	4.5594			
Experience in PHC	0-5	4.0767	0.332	0.856	Not significant
	6-10	4.1884			
	11-15	4.1852			
	16-20	4.1786			
	21 and more	4.1692			
marital status	Single	4.1806	0.336	0.715	Not significant
	Married	4.1652			
	Divorce	4.0000			
Post MBBS Qualification	Nil	4.1324	1.086	0.365	Not significant
	Diploma	4.2231			
	Master	4.2939			
	Board of equivalent	4.0949			
	Fellowship equivalent	4.1596			
Nationality	Saudi	4.1833	0.191	0.826	Not significant
	Non-Saudi (Arabic speaking)	4.1483			
	Non-Saudi (Non-Arabic speaking)	4.1269			
Position	Senior House Officer (SHO)	3.8786	1.533	0.195	Not significant
	Resident	4.2147			
	Registrar	4.1821			
	Senior Registrar	4.1958			
	Consultant	4.1800			

Discussion

The Patient Experience Program is one of the critical initiatives in the transformation process in the health sector within the Saudi Vision 2030 because of its importance in measuring the quality of health services provided. Moreover, it is among the strategic goals of the Department of Health Services in the Ministry of Defense. Since primary health care physicians are the first line of contact with the patient, they play an important and sensitive role in improving the patient's experience [33].

From this point of view, this study was conducted to measure the attitudes of primary health care doctors and to determine the level of their practice towards the

patient experience program in the health centers of Prince Sultan Military Medical City.

This study found that primary health care physicians' attitudes are positive (high level), as measured by their Agreement and beliefs about the concepts of the patient experience program that were reached by previous studies and research.

Regarding the difference in the Attitude of PHC physicians toward patient experience due to demographic variables, there are statistically significant differences between the Attitudes of PHC Physicians toward Patient Experience due to position.

It was found that SHO physicians have the lowest level of Attitude about patient experience among their colleagues in the category of consultants, residents,

registrars, and senior registrars. However, there is no statistically significant difference between qualifications, the number of years of experience, or other demographic variables. This may be due to work pressure as they get the essential duty of working hours, which causes them to be discouraged from quality aspects, including the patient experience.

The vast majority of physicians strongly agreed that patient experience is defined as a reflection of the events that occur in the care process and, therefore, provides relevant information about the performance of the healthcare system and workers to meet the needs of the patient) [3,4] as the highest relative consensus. This indicates their good knowledge of the definition of the patient experience. They also agreed that communication between the Physician and patient is a significant component of Patient Satisfaction that can affect overall satisfaction as the second-highest percentage of Agreement, which enhances the patient's satisfaction level [20].

Regarding administrative support in health facilities, most doctors see the importance of the supervisor's support for employees, which positively impacts the patient's experience, as mentioned in a study [28]. So, health center managers need to realize this point by supporting their doctors because it improves the patient experience.

Participants demonstrated a high level of belief that Patient Experience provides relevant information about the performance of the healthcare system and workers to meet the needs of the patient and, therefore, includes pertinent information about the performance of the healthcare system and workers to meet the needs of the patient [3,4]. This study also showed that Physician-patient communication, a core measure of patient-centered care, is strongly associated with better clinical health outcomes [38,39]; this is reflected in the patient's trust in PHC centers through clear and effective communication. While patients with a lower level of confidence in their Physician are more likely to report that requested or needed services are not provided [40]. which means that physicians must be trained in communication skills as a prerequisite for excellence in patient experience.

The patient's opinion through the patient experience survey is essential in evaluating primary health care centers, as indicated by a study [21]. in addition to the position of the participants in this study. This is because patient experience is an essential outcome of healthcare quality from the participants' perspective in this study, consistent with Holland's opinion (2008). Also, participants believe that Patient-reported experiences are vital to improving the quality of care, as shown in a study [3,4].

The participants in this study believe that physicians answering patient questions is the highest predictor of

the overall rating in the patient experience. This calls for physicians to pay attention to patients' questions and be aware of improving the patient experience [30]. In addition, they consider Patient experience to be a measure of patient-centeredness, one of six healthcare quality aims proposed by the Institute of Medicine (IOM) [6].

In the lowest consensus rate among the recommendations of previous studies in the field of patient experience, participants believed that the Saudi Central Board for Accreditation of Healthcare Institutions (CBAHI) should enhance physician-patient communication as part of their standards for accrediting PHCs as recommended by [30].

The above results show us the positive Attitude of primary health care physicians towards the patient experience through their firm belief in the most prominent concepts of patient experience gleaned from previous studies and research, which is attributed to the fact that the problem of low level of satisfaction of patients is not due to the attitudes of doctors, but maybe due to other influential factors. Therefore, the researcher believes that the level of PHC physicians' Practice in clinics should be measured through questions about their behavior with patients, the elements of which were extracted from the patient experience evaluation survey provided by Press Ganey/Health Link [36].

The participants showed a high level of practice performance towards the patient experience by answering questions measuring the level of practice in dealing with the patient. Due to demographic variables, there are no statistically significant differences between the Practice of physicians toward patient Experience. This result does not reflect the level of evaluation of the patient's experience in primary health care centers in PSMMC; as we also mentioned in the result of measuring the Attitude, it may be due to other factors affecting the evaluation of the service provided to the patient that must be taken into account.

Due to the lack of previous studies measuring health practitioners' attitudes and practices towards patient experience, whether locally or globally, it was impossible to compare the study's results regarding the research question.

Conclusion

The Patient Experience Program is one of the modern programs launched recently in the Medical Services Department of the Ministry of Defense (MSD), and they are part of the National Transformation Program in the health sector because of its importance in raising the level of performance in health facilities and providing health services of the highest quality standards.

This study aimed to assess the level of attitudes of PHC physicians about the patient's experience in PSMMC, as they are the first line of contact with the patient.

This study showed that PHC physicians in PSMHC had a positive attitude toward patient experience. With a statistically significant difference in the level of the SHO physicians category from the rest of their colleagues from the other positions. Without the presence of any statistically significant differences in other demographic factors.

Recommendations

After conducting this study and reviewing many previous studies, we recommend the following:

- To set up a patient experience section in each primary health center to analyze and set standards for measuring patient experience.
- Establish training programs for PHC physicians, especially SHOs, to familiarize them with the basics of the patient experience and improve their communication skills with patients.
- Orienting doctors to the importance of dealing with the patient is one of the pillars of the quality of health care and is reflected in the level of the patient's experience.
- Finally, we recommend that PHC physicians become familiar with the items of patient experience evaluation so that they can focus on them and consider their aspects when dealing with patients.
- There is a need for more research studies that assess the knowledge, attitudes, and practices of healthcare workers regarding the patient experience. Such studies can include evaluating these aspects among healthcare workers, such as nurses, pharmacists, reception staff, appointment personnel, and patient relations staff.

References

- [1] The Beryl Institute. The state of patient experience. Available at: www.theberylinstitute.org/store/ViewProduct.aspx?id=14795937
- [2] Ozcelik A, Varnali K, Burnaz S. A holistic framework for patient experience: 5P model. *International Journal Of Pharmaceutical And Healthcare Marketing*, 2021;15(4):516-533. doi: 10.1108/ijphm-05-2020-0042
- [3] Kieft RA, de Brouwer BB, Francke AL, Delnoij DM. How nurses and their work environment affect patient experiences of the quality of care: a qualitative study. *BMC Health Serv Res*. 2014 Jun 13;14:249. doi: 10.1186/1472-6963-14-249
- [4] Price D. Patients' Experiences of Attending Emergency Departments Where Primary Care Services Are Located: Qualitative Findings from Patient and Clinician Interviews from a Realist Evaluation. *BMC Emergency Medicine*, 2022. doi: 10.1186/s12873-021-00562-9
- [5] Evans RG, Edwards A, Evans S, Elwyn B, Elwyn G. Assessing the practising physician using patient surveys: a systematic review of instruments and

feedback methods. *Fam Pract*. 2007 Apr;24(2):117-27. doi: 10.1093/fampra/cml072

- [6] Relman A. Book Review Crossing the Quality Chasm: A New Health System for the 21st Century By the Committee on Quality of Health Care in America of the Institute of Medicine. Washington, D.C., National Academy Press; 2001.
- [7] Institute of Medicine. Crossing the Quality Chasm: A New Health System for the 21st Century. Washington, DC: National Academies Press; 2001.
- [8] Zavareh D. Client Perception on Quality Improvement in Health Care Services and Patient Satisfaction. *Public Health Open Access*, 2017;1(2). doi: 10.23880/phoa-16000111
- [9] Holland K. Proposed changes for nurse education in England (UK) as a result of the Darzi report (DoH, 2008a) Health Quality Care for All--NHS next stage review final report: some initial observations. *Nurse Educ Pract*. 2008 Sep;8(5):299-301. doi: 10.1016/j.nepr.2008.07.004
- [10] Doyle C, Lennox L, Bell D. A systematic review of evidence on the links between patient experience and clinical safety and effectiveness. *BMJ Open*. 2013 Jan 3;3(1):e001570. doi: 10.1136/bmjopen-2012-001570
- [11] Nash D, Joshi M, Ransom E, Ransom S. The healthcare quality book (4th ed., p. 233). Health Administration Press, Chicago, Illinois Association of University Programs in Health Administration, Washington, DC; 2019
- [12] Roter DL. Patient participation in the patient-provider interaction: the effects of patient question asking on the quality of interaction, satisfaction and compliance. *Health Educ Monogr*. 1977 Winter;5(4):281-315. doi: 10.1177/109019817700500402
- [13] Bartlett EE, Grayson M, Barker R, Levine DM, Golden A, Libber S. The effects of physician communications skills on patient satisfaction; recall, and adherence. *J Chronic Dis*. 1984;37(9-10):755-64. doi: 10.1016/0021-9681(84)90044-4
- [14] Roberts M, Campbell J, Abel, G, et al. Understanding high and low patient experience scores in primary care: analysis of patients' survey data for general practices and individual doctors. *BMJ*, 2014;349(nov11-3):g6034-g6034. doi: 10.1136/bmj.g6034
- [15] Edwards A, Evans R, White P, Elwyn G. Experiencing patient-experience surveys: a qualitative study of the accounts of GPs. *Br J Gen Pract*. 2011 Apr;61(585):157-66. doi: 10.3399/bjgp11X567072
- [16] Cheraghi-Sohi S, Bower P. Can the feedback of patient assessments, brief training, or their combination, improve the interpersonal skills of primary care physicians? A systematic review. *BMC*

Health Serv Res. 2008 Aug 21;8:179. doi: 10.1186/1472-6963-8-179

[17] Farrington C, Burt J, Boiko O, Campbell J, Roland M. Doctors' engagements with patient experience surveys in primary and secondary care: a qualitative study. *Health Expect*. 2017 Jun;20(3):385-394. doi: 10.1111/hex.12465

[18] Marcinowicz L, Chlabicz S, Grebowski R. Understanding patient satisfaction with family doctor care. *J Eval Clin Pract*. 2010 Aug;16(4):712-5. doi: 10.1111/j.1365-2753.2009.01180.x

[19] Cao YJ, Chen D, Liu Y, Smith M. Disparities in the Use of In-Person and Telehealth Primary Care Among High- and Low-Risk Medicare Beneficiaries During COVID-19. *J Patient Exp*. 2021 Dec 13;8:23743735211065274. doi: 10.1177/23743735211065274

[20] Kumah E. Patient experience and satisfaction with a healthcare system: connecting the dots. *International Journal Of Healthcare Management*, 2017;12(3):173–179. doi: 10.1080/20479700.2017.1353776

[21] Polluste K. Primary health care system in transition: the patient's experience. *International Journal For Quality In Health Care*, 2000;12(6):503–509. doi: 10.1093/intqhc/12.6.503

[22] Wong E, Mavondo F, Fisher J. Patient feedback to improve quality of patient-centred care in public hospitals: a systematic review of the evidence. *BMC Health Serv Res*. 2020 Jun 11;20(1):530. doi: 10.1186/s12913-020-05383-3

[23] Asprey A, Campbell JL, Newbould J, Cohn S, Carter M, Davey A, Roland M. Challenges to the credibility of patient feedback in primary healthcare settings: a qualitative study. *Br J Gen Pract*. 2013 Mar;63(608):e200-8. doi: 10.3399/bjgp13X664252

[24] Macnaughton J. *General Practice and Ethics: Uncertainty and Responsibility*: Edited by Christopher Dowrick and Lucy Frith, London, Routledge, 1999, 196 pages, pound14.99. *Journal Of Medical Ethics*, 2000;26(6):479-a-480. doi: 10.1136/jme.26.6.479-a

[25] Sixma HJ, Spreeuwenberg PM, van der Pasch MA. Patient satisfaction with the general practitioner: a two-level analysis. *Med Care*. 1998 Feb;36(2):212-29. doi: 10.1097/00005650-199802000-00010

[26] Gibbons E, Graham C, King J, Flott K, Jenkinson C, Fitzpatrick R. Developing approaches to collecting and using evidence of patient experience below the level of national surveys. *Patient Experience Journal*, 2016;3(1):92–100. doi: 10.35680/2372-0247.1118

[27] Browne K, Roseman D, Shaller D, Edgman-Levitan S. Analysis & commentary. Measuring patient experience as a strategy for improving primary care. *Health Aff (Millwood)*. 2010 May;29(5):921-5. doi: 10.1377/hlthaff.2010.0238

[28] Ogbonnaya C, Babalola MT. A closer look at how managerial support can help improve patient experience: Insights from the U.K.'s National Health Service. *Human Relations*, 2021;74(11):1820–1840. doi: 10.1177/0018726720938834

[29] Odhayani AA, Khawaja RA. Patient's Satisfaction: Insight into Access to Service, Interpersonal Communication and Quality of Care Issues. *Middle East Journal of Family Medicine*, 2014;12:24–30. doi: 10.5742/MEWFM.2014.92558

[30] Senitan M, Gillespie J. Health-Care Reform in Saudi Arabia: Patient Experience at Primary Health-Care Centers. *J Patient Exp*. 2020 Aug;7(4):587-592. doi: 10.1177/2374373519872420

[31] Almutairi KM. Culture and language differences as a barrier to provision of quality care by the health workforce in Saudi Arabia. *Saudi Med J*. 2015 Apr;36(4):425-31. doi: 10.15537/smj.2015.4.10133

[32] Senitan M, Alhaiti AH, Gillespie J. Patient satisfaction and experience of primary care in Saudi Arabia: a systematic review. *Int J Qual Health Care*. 2018 Dec 1;30(10):751-759. doi: 10.1093/intqhc/mzy104

[33] Health Sector Transformation Program. *Vision 2030*. Available at: <https://www.vision2030.gov.sa/v2030/vrps/hstp/>; 2021.

[34] Jarallah JS. Referral from primary care to hospitals in Saudi Arabia: 1) quality of referral letters and feedback reports. *J Family Community Med*. 1998 Jul;5(2):15-22.

[35] Health-Links. *Health-links*. Me. Available at: <https://www.health-links.me/web/index.html>; 2021

[36] Gress Ganey: *Healthcare Experience Analytics*. *Pressganey.com*. Available at: <https://www.pressganey.com/>; 2022.

[37] Kohn LT, Corrigan JM, Donaldson MS. (eds.). *To Err Is Human: Building a Safer Health System*. Washington, DC: National Academies Press; 2000.

[38] Roter DL. Patient participation in the patient-provider interaction: the effects of patient question asking on the quality of interaction, satisfaction and compliance. *Health Educ Monogr*. 1977 Winter;5(4):281-315. doi: 10.1177/109019817700500402

[39] Bartlett EE, Grayson M, Barker R, Levine DM, Golden A, Libber S. The effects of physician communications skills on patient satisfaction; recall, and adherence. *J Chronic Dis*. 1984;37(9-10):755-64. doi: 10.1016/0021-9681(84)90044-4

[40] Thom DH, Kravitz RL, Bell RA, Krupat E, Azari R. Patient trust in the physician: relationship to patient requests. *Fam Pract*. 2002 Oct;19(5):476-83. doi: 10.1093/fampra/19.5.476

